

Concept of the Working Group “Long Term Access and Preservation (LTA)” in the NFDI Section “Common Infrastructures”

Name of the working group

Long Term Access and Preservation

Acronym

LTA

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Abstract

Long-term access and preservation (LTA)¹ for each kind of digital resource has been a recurring problem for over 30 years and requires an ongoing investment of resources, as well as an ongoing adaptation of processes to the ever-changing technological capabilities and needs. At the same time it gains urgency with the exponential growth and complexity of research data, whether it involves demands from funders or from science itself, business, or society. The retention terms depend on these requirements. The DFG requirement² to keep research data available “at least” for 10 years from creation demands for a minimal archival period. Still, longer retention times can apply, up to permanence, as is usual for cultural or arts and humanities data, geology, certain biosphere and climate data.

NFDI consortia have a variety of disparate and distributed information infrastructures that share a high potential of interoperability. A major goal of NFDI is to use this potential to create a Research Data Commons (RDC)³. The evolving RDC concept includes shared cloud services, an application layer with access to high-performance computing (HPC) and other external services, collaborative workspaces, terminology services, and a common authentication and authorization infrastructure (AAI). The necessary interoperability of services requires, in particular, agreement on protocols and standards, the specification of workflows and interfaces, and the definition of long-term sustainable responsibilities for overarching services and deliverables. This is demanding if one regards single infrastructure components which might be well-tested in NFDI on a domain-specific basis, but are quite heterogeneous and diverse between domains.

Against this background, the integration of LTA into the RDC of the NFDI is an urgent desideratum in order to be able to guarantee the permanent availability and usability of research data.⁴ A distinction must be made between the archiving of digital objects as “a physical object, a logical object, and a conceptual object”.⁵ The most important task is to record the semantic and software-technical context in which these objects perform. The working group “aims to identify and harmonize methods, procedures, and techniques for long-term preservation and use of data and software as reproducible information objects” from which a digital preservation base service may be developed.⁶ Parts of relevant requirements specified by consortia have already been set as national or international

¹ The concept uses LTA for long-term access and preservation for the tasks and responsibilities the OAIS standard covers (“ISO 14721:2012. Open Archival Information System (OAIS) Reference Model’ 2012; The Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems (CCSDS) 2012 Reference Model for an Open Archival Information System (OAIS) Recommended Practice CCSDS 650.0-M-2”; CCSDS (2024) “Reference Model for an Open Archival Information System (OAIS) Recommended Practice CCSDS 650.0-M-3” <https://public.ccsds.org/Pubs/650x0m3.pdf>). The international community uses digital preservation and long-term preservation.

² DFG (2015) “DFG Guidelines on the Handling of Research Data” <https://www.dfg.de/resource/blob/172098/b08fcad16f1ff5ddca967f1ebde3a8c3/guidelines-research-data-data.pdf>

³ NFDI Cross-cutting Topics Workshop Report, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4593769>

⁴ German Council for Scientific Information Infrastructures (2016) Enhancing Research Data Management: Performance through Diversity. Recommendations regarding structures, processes, and financing for research data management in Germany“, Recommendations 4.3, p. 39ff. <http://nbn-resolving.de/urn:nbn:de:101:1-20161214992>

⁵ Thibodeau, K. „The State of Digital Preservation: An International Perspective, chapter Overview of Technological Approaches to Digital Preservation and Challenges in Coming Years“, Report Number 31, CLIR, 2002. <https://www.clir.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/6/pub107.pdf>

⁶ Diepenbroek and Schimmler (2024) “Concept of the Section “Common Infrastructures” - section-infra” Version 2.0

standards like ISO 14721, ISO 16363, ISO 17068, ISO 24143, the CoreTrustSeal, DIN 31644 and DIN 31645 or frameworks like the TRUST principles⁷. To ensure professional LTA, it is paramount to understand these principles and apply them to the pertinent data. NFDI consortia must be enabled to cater for their needs with regard to content preservation by taking existing research data services into account and evaluating them in context of these principles.

Consequently, as long as sufficient resources are available, the working group will promote LTA-awareness and provide consultation for consortia. Furthermore, the working group intends to recommend suitable LTA-focused standards to NFDI and the Research Data Commons, as well as input to RDC development on the technical level. It may focus on quality control and provenance and intends to expand international networking and participation in developing international resources relevant for LTA.

The working group assembles members of various NFDI consortia covering the arts and humanities, sciences and engineering disciplines and experts from a variety of related infrastructures with strong connections to the nestor digital preservation competence network.⁸ The close linkage of NFDI consortia with partners in the field of LTA brings together two required areas of expertise: a) that of the state of the art of LTA and b) the knowledge of data producers about contexts of data origin and data users. This composition enables the group to do both: to take an overarching view that spans the requirements of the disciplines and consortia and to take into account interdisciplinary needs, and at the same time brings in the existing know-how into the infrastructure sector.

Motivation and Objectives

Since the inception of the digital age, the creation of digital data and documents has been accompanied by problems of accessibility, obsolescence or even loss. Valuable data has disappeared from servers because of negligence or technical failure. Well known examples are corrupted tapes and loss of data of NASA's first space missions.⁹ But even if data is extant after a couple of years, quite often using or simply accessing the data can be difficult or almost impossible due to obsolete or proprietary formats, lack of documentation, missing tools or dysfunctional hardware.

The problem is not confined to some rare instances, it permeates all areas of research where data is produced and stored on e.g. institutional servers that, after funding has ended and the researchers involved have moved away to new jobs and projects, nobody maintains any more. Data that would have been useful for the next generation of researchers is no longer available, references may not resolve anymore, or in some cases research results cannot be reproduced as the pertinent information is missing and irreproducible, unique and valuable

⁷ Lin, D., Crabtree, J., Dillo, I. *et al.* The TRUST Principles for digital repositories. *Sci Data* **7**, 144 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>, RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption Working Group <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rdawds-trust-principles-outreach-and-adoption-working-group/activity/>

⁸ https://www.langzeitarchivierung.de/Webs/nestor/DE/Home/home_node.html

⁹ "Because the WNRC no longer stored the Apollo-era tapes, Nafzger could draw only one conclusion based on what he read in the weeklies: The 45 Apollo 11 tapes were degaussed, recertified, and reused to satisfy a NASA-wide shortage of one-inch tapes more than a decade later. NASA's M-22 recordings of the Apollo 11 moonwalk likely were gone forever." https://web.archive.org/web/20140802233214/http://www.nasa.gov/pdf/398311main_Apollo_11_Report.pdf

data may even be permanently lost. Preserving research data and its provenance, therefore, is paramount to avoid repeating expensive experiments and wasting valuable resources, to allow re-purposing data, to obtain proof of the validity of former research results as well as maintain the evidence trail via scientific references in publications. LTA, however, is more than just creating backup files or taking precautions against data loss or intruders (bitstream preservation) as the typical work of data centers. The greatest challenge of LTA is not so much the preservation of the bit stream, but the preservation of information on a logical and semantic level (content preservation)^{10,11}. This kind of information preservation can be achieved generally by two methods: migration and emulation. While the former is used to transform data and content to current standards and formats, the latter attempts to emulate environments allowing to keep e.g. outdated software running. Both strategies lean on technical metadata and rights information that are stored along with the data. Similarly, content preservation can only succeed with appropriate content-related, event-driven metadata, which is ideally already available when the data is created.

Most solutions addressing LTA draw on the OAIS model (ISO 14721:2012) describing the ingestion, archival proper and dissemination process of documents and data (SIP (Submission Information Package), AIP (Archival Information Package) and DIP (Dissemination Information Package)).¹² There is a variety of software solutions available adopting the OAIS model such as Artefactual Archivematica¹³, DIMAG (Digitales Magazin)¹⁴, DiPS (Digital Preservation Solution)¹⁵, ExLibris Rosetta¹⁶, Libnova LibSafe¹⁷, Preservica¹⁸, or VITAM¹⁹ that integrate other LTA services such as the file format registry PRONOM²⁰, DROID (Digital Record and Object Identification)²¹, or JHOVE²² for identifying and validating file formats. In addition, there are communities, in Germany especially nestor (participants of the group are members of nestor), on the international level especially the Open Preservation Foundation (OPF) and the Digital Preservation Coalition (dpc), that have already successfully developed LTA strategies and policies the working group can draw upon. In addition,

¹⁰ Thibodeau, K. „The State of Digital Preservation: An International Perspective, chapter Overview of Technological Approaches to Digital Preservation and Challenges in Coming Years“, Report Number 31, CLIR, 2002. <https://www.clir.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/6/pub107.pdf>.

¹¹ Lindlar et al. 2020. “You Say Potato, I Say Potato” Mapping Digital Preservation and Research Data Management Concepts towards Collective Curation and Preservation Strategies’. *International Journal of Digital Curation* 15 (1): 26. <https://doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v15i1.728>.

¹² CCSDS (2024) “Reference Model for an Open Archival Information System (OAIS) Recommended Practice CCSDS 650.0-M-3” <https://public.ccsds.org/Pubs/650x0m3.pdf>. Update of the ISO standard is in progress at the beginning of 2025.

¹³ <https://www.archivematica.org/en/>

¹⁴ <https://dimag-wiki.la-bw.de/public/>

¹⁵ <https://www.stadt-koeln.de/artikel/62898/index.html>

¹⁶ <https://knowledge.exlibrisgroup.com/Rosetta>

¹⁷ <https://libnova.com/>

¹⁸ <https://preservica.com/>

¹⁹ <https://github.com/ProgrammeVitam>

²⁰ <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM/Default.aspx>

²¹ <https://digital-preservation.github.io/droid/>

²² <https://github.com/openpreserve/jhove/>

international working groups such as those under the umbrellas of the Research Data Alliance (RDA) and the EOSC (European Open Science Cloud), deal with different issues pertaining to the lifecycle management and digital preservation of research data.

The working group LTA aims to improve digital preservation of research data in the context of NFDI. After evaluating needs in relation to digital preservation in various NFDI consortia²³, a central digital preservation service for research data in Germany was deemed unsuitable at the present time. Consortia, institutions and state initiatives already provide services for research data or are currently being established. These services may cover only specific aspects of digital preservation (e. g. providing only bitstream preservation, providing both bitstream and content preservation but with spatial or topical restrictions) and may provide only limited personnel support for preservation tasks. Accordingly, the working group aims to improve digital preservation by

1. supporting NFDI consortia towards establishing content preservation and meeting consortia needs,
2. identify, promote and adopt suitable standards for archival purposes within NFDI and
3. promote integration of digital preservation solutions in Research Data Commons.

Regarding aim (1.), supporting consortia may involve answering questions raised by consortia and discussing solutions. Extensively supporting and pro-actively approaching consortia is out of scope for the working group but an additionally funded consultation service may provide such services. The consultation service seeks to establish a common understanding of how various kinds of data are created, collected or selected by NFDI consortia and how they are stored and documented by appropriate metadata and according to the OAIS principles. In order to approach this, it will draw on work already done by stakeholders like nector and established discipline-specific solutions. It also may collect typical use cases for the application of migration or emulation procedures. In addition, the consultation service will address issues of data sovereignty, cost calculation, scaling of services and implementation. In particular it is planned to describe and conceive single services suitable for NFDI LTA, to develop a financial and organizational model for ensuring sustainability and long-term operation of the resources and services brought into the NFDI. The consultation service will also promote certification which addresses digital preservation best practices, among them sustainability of infrastructures and services, sustained responsibility and risk evaluation like in the context of loss of sovereignty.

For the second and third aim, i. e. working on standards and promoting solution for the RDC, suitable standards for LTA in NFDI such as PREMIS²⁴ (to be aligned with other NFDI sections such as metadata and to be connected to international initiatives such as OPF²⁵ , RDA²⁶ or

²³ Markus, K., Naumann, K., Schmalzl, M., Watson, J., & Triebel, D. (2024). Long-term Archiving in the NFDI. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11109480>

²⁴ <https://www.loc.gov/standards/premis/>

²⁵ <https://openpreservation.org/>

²⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

dpc²⁷) and international recommendations will be taken into account²⁸. Activities on long term preservation of research data - after agreed on a national level - will well align with the concept of discipline-specific national data infrastructures, for example as described by Güntsch et al. (2024, base infrastructure)²⁹ for biodiversity discipline and thus will be of benefit for evolving Research Data Commons architecture. Metadata standards and recommendations in digital preservation such as PREMIS and “Information Preparation to Enable Long Term Use (IPELTU)”³⁰ specifically support provenance documentation and audit trail information and as such support NFDI’s aim to improve in this area. The working group will also aim at international cooperations with suitable EOSC task forces and projects and further initiatives, such as the Digital Curation Centre. It may also take non-preservation standards and concepts into consideration³¹ and may participate in developing standards further, if resources are available.

The working group may also contribute to the development of the Research Data Commons on a conceptual level, specifically regarding quality control processes e. g. in relation to automatic file validation processes. As digital preservation is based on risk management, the risk being data loss, various best practices and standards can be applied to processes presently that may reduce data loss in the long-term and support long-term reusability.

²⁷ <https://www.dpconline.org/>, <https://planets-project.eu/>

²⁸ The folder LZA-Initiativen_Ressourcen_(UAG_BigPicture) contains a document with a collection of relevant standards, among other information https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1ux3jO1qRK9_pS6aOEKvSVQxYOL6mobbT. Furthermore, see also <https://dilcis.eu/>

²⁹ Güntsch, A. et. al. (2024), National biodiversity data infrastructures: ten essential functions for science, policy, and practice, *BioScience*, 2024;, biae109, <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biae109>

³⁰ CCSDS (2024) Information Preparation to Enable Long Term Use (IPELTU) CCSDS 653.0-M-1. <https://public.ccsds.org/Pubs/653x0m1.pdf>

³¹ e. g. <https://www.dona.net/digitalobjectarchitecture>